

Application Of Neutrosophic Sets Based On Neutrosophic Negative Score Function in Medical Diagnosis

Thangaraja P¹, Vadivel A^{2,3,*} and John Sundar C³

¹Department of Mathematics, Mahendra Engineering college, Namakkal - 637 503, India;
thangarajap1991@gmail.com

²Department of Mathematics, Arignar Anna Government Arts College, Namakkal - 637 002, India;
avmaths@gmail.com

³Department of Mathematics, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar - 608 002, India;
johnphdau@hotmail.com

*Correspondence: (Vadivel A) avmaths@gmail.com; Tel.: (+91 9442353356)

Abstract. Medical diagnosis is the process of determining which illness or disease is causing an individual's symptoms and warning signs. It is most commonly referred to as analysis, with the clinical environment implied. The evidence required for discovery is typically acquired from a clinical study and an examination of the individual seeking medical treatment. The major purpose of this research is to use topology to establish a methodical technique for decision making difficulties in order to select the appropriate attributes and alternatives for neutrosophic negative score function. In addition, we use a neutrosophic topological space based on attributes and alternatives, as well as graphical representation, to apply a neutrosophic negative score function in medical diagnosis problems.

Keywords: Neutrosophic set, Neutrosophic topology, Neutrosophic topological spaces, Neutrosophic negative score function.

1. Introduction

Zadeh [41] as part of logic and set hypothesis was the first to introduce the concept of a fuzzy set between intervals in mathematics. Chang's [10] general topology framework, that utilises fuzzy topological space, was created with a fuzzy set. Adlassnig [6] used fuzzy set theory to formalise medical interactions and fuzzy logic to create a framework for automated analysis. This theory has been used in the areas of artificial intelligence, probability, science, control structures, and financial concerns [16, 20, 26].

In 1983, Atanassov [7] developed an intuitionistic fuzzy set with membership and non-membership values. Coker [14] created intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces from intuitionistic fuzzy sets. De et al. [15] were the first to develop the applications of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in medical diagnosis. Several researchers [8,17,27] investigated intuitionistic fuzzy sets in medical diagnostics further.

Smarandache [23,24] offered the notions of neutrosophy and neutrosophic set at the beginning of the 21th century and has a wide range of consistent applications in computer science, information systems, applied mathematics, artificial intelligence, mechanics, medicine, dynamic, management science, and electrical & electronics, etc [1–4,36,37]. Salama and Alblowi, [21,22] in 2012, developed neutrosophic set and neutrosophic crisp set in a neutrosophic topological space. Recently, Vadivel and authors [29,30,33–35] presented various open sets and mappings in neutrosophic topological spaces. Smarandache [24] described the single valued Neutrosophic set on three portions (T-Truth, F-Falsehood, I-Indeterminacy) Neutrosophic sets, which Wang et al. [38] worked on. In decision making problems, Majumdar and Samanta [18] described various similarity measures of single valued neutrosophic sets. Several researchers have recently proposed numerous similarity measures and single-valued neutrosophic sets in medical diagnostics [5,9,11–13,19,28,39,40]. Vadivel and authors [31,32] discussed an applications using neutrosophic score function in mobile networking and material selection problems.

The methodical strategy for decision making issues to identify the appropriate qualities and alternatives for neutrosophic negative score function by employing topology is defined in this work. In addition, we use neutrosophic topological spaces to apply a neutrosophic negative score function in medical diagnosis problems based on their features and alternatives.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [21] Let T be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic set (briefly, $N_s\text{eus}$) L is an object having the form $L = \{\langle t, \mu_L(t), \sigma_L(t), \nu_L(t) \rangle : t \in T\}$ where $\mu_L, \sigma_L, \nu_L \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denote the degree of membership, indeterminacy, non-membership functions respectively of each element $t \in T$ to the $N_s\text{eus}$ L and $0 \leq \mu_L(t) + \sigma_L(t) + \nu_L(t) \leq 3$ for each $t \in T$.

Definition 2.2. [21] Let T be a non-empty set & the $N_s\text{eus}$'s L & K in the form $L = \{\langle t, \mu_L(t), \sigma_L(t), \nu_L(t) \rangle : t \in T\}$, $K = \{\langle t, \mu_K(t), \sigma_K(t), \nu_K(t) \rangle : t \in T\}$, then

- (i) $0_{N_s} = \langle t, 0, 0, 1 \rangle$ and $1_{N_s} = \langle t, 1, 1, 0 \rangle$,
- (ii) $L \subseteq K$ iff $\mu_L(t) \leq \mu_K(t)$, $\sigma_L(t) \leq \sigma_K(t)$ & $\nu_L(t) \geq \nu_K(t) : t \in T$,
- (iii) $L = K$ iff $L \subseteq K$ and $K \subseteq L$,
- (iv) $1_{N_s} - L = \{\langle t, \nu_L(t), 1 - \sigma_L(t), \mu_L(t) \rangle : t \in T\} = L^c$,
- (v) $L \cup K = \{\langle t, \max(\mu_L(t), \mu_K(t)), \max(\sigma_L(t), \sigma_K(t)), \min(\nu_L(t), \nu_K(t)) \rangle : t \in T\}$,
- (vi) $L \cap K = \{\langle t, \min(\mu_L(t), \mu_K(t)), \min(\sigma_L(t), \sigma_K(t)), \max(\nu_L(t), \nu_K(t)) \rangle : t \in T\}$.

Definition 2.3. [21] A neutrosophic topology (briefly, $N_s\text{euty}$) on a non-empty set T is a family Γ_{N_s} of neutrosophic subsets of T satisfying

- (i) $0_{N_s}, 1_{N_s} \in \Gamma_{N_s}$.
- (ii) $L_1 \cap L_2 \in \Gamma_{N_s}$ for any $L_1, L_2 \in \Gamma_{N_s}$.
- (iii) $\bigcup L_x \in \Gamma_{N_s}, \forall L_x : x \in T \subseteq \Gamma_{N_s}$.

Then (T, Γ_{N_s}) is called a neutrosophic topological space (briefly, $N_s\text{eutysp}$) in T . The Γ_{N_s} elements are called neutrosophic open sets (briefly, $N_s\text{euos}$) in T . A $N_s\text{eus } C_{N_s}$ is called a neutrosophic closed sets (briefly, $N_s\text{eucs}$) iff its complement $C_{N_s}^c$ is $N_s\text{euos}$.

Definition 2.4. [25] The Neutrosophic Negative Score Function (briefly, $N_s\text{euNeScFu}$) on $s : L \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined by

$$s(\mu_L, \sigma_L, \nu_L) = \frac{1 - \mu_L + \sigma_L + \nu_L}{3}$$

that represents the average of positiveness of the neutrosophic components μ_L, σ_L, ν_L .

3. Neutrosophic Negative Score Function

In this section, we provide a neutrosophic scoring function that is based on a methodical approach to solving a decision-making problem with neutrosophic information. In the decision-making situation, the following vital stages are recommended as the precise technique to deal with selecting the appropriate qualities and alternative based on neutrosophic negative score function.

Step 1: Problem field selection:

Consider multi-attribute decision making problems with m attributes At_1, At_2, \dots, At_m and n alternatives $\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_n$ and p attributes $\nu_1, \nu_2, \dots, \nu_p, (n \leq p)$.

	τ_1	τ_2	. . .	τ_n		At_1	At_2	. . .	At_m
At_1	(b_{11})	(b_{12})	. . .	(b_{1n})	ν_1	(e_{11})	(e_{12})	. . .	(e_{1m})
At_2	(b_{21})	(b_{22})	. . .	(b_{2n})	ν_2	(e_{21})	(e_{22})	. . .	(e_{2m})
.
.
.
At_m	(b_{m1})	(b_{m2})	. . .	(b_{mn})	ν_p	(e_{p1})	(e_{p2})	. . .	(e_{pm})

Here all the attributes b_{ij} and e_{ki} are neutrosophic numbers, where $(i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, p)$.

Step 2: From neutrosophic topologies for τ_j and ν_k :

(i) $\tau_j^* = \tau \cup \tau^* \cup \tau^{**}$, where $\tau = \{1_{N_s}, 0_{N_s}, b_{1j}, b_{2j}, \dots, b_{mj}\}$, $\tau^* = \{b_{1j} \cup b_{2j}, b_{2j} \cup b_{3j}, \dots, b_{m-1j} \cup b_{mj}\}$ and $\tau^{**} = \{b_{1j} \cap b_{2j}, b_{2j} \cap b_{3j}, \dots, b_{m-1j} \cap b_{mj}\}$.

(ii) $\nu_j^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}$, where $\nu = \{1_{N_s}, 0_{N_s}, e_{k1}, e_{k2}, \dots, e_{km}\}$, $\nu^* = \{e_{k1} \cup e_{k2}, e_{k2} \cup e_{k3}, \dots, e_{km-1} \cup e_{km}\}$ and $\nu^{**} = \{e_{k1} \cap e_{k2}, e_{k2} \cap e_{k3}, \dots, e_{km-1} \cap e_{km}\}$.

Step 3: Find neutrosophic negative score functions:

Neutrosophic negative score functions (shortly, $N_s euNeScFu$) of $\tau, \tau^*, \tau^{**}, \nu, \nu^*, \nu^{**}, \tau_j$ and ν_k are defined as follows.

(i) $N_s euNeScFu(\tau) = \frac{1}{3(m+2)} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{m+2} [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$,
 $N_s euNeScFu(\tau^*) = \frac{1}{3q} \left[\sum_{i=1}^q [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$, where q is the number of element of τ^* and
 $N_s euNeScFu(\tau^{**}) = \frac{1}{3r} \left[\sum_{i=1}^r [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$, where r is the number of element of τ^{**} . For
 $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$,

$N_s euNeScFu(\tau_j)$

$$= \begin{cases} N_s euNeScFu(\tau) & \text{if } N_s euNeScFu(\tau^*) = 0; N_s euNeScFu(\tau^{**}) = 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} [N_s euNeScFu(\tau) + N_s euNeScFu(\tau^*)] & \text{if } N_s euNeScFu(\tau^{**}) = 0 \\ \frac{1}{3} [N_s euNeScFu(\tau) + N_s euNeScFu(\tau^*) + N_s euNeScFu(\tau^{**})] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

(ii) $N_s euNeScFu(\nu) = \frac{1}{3(m+2)} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{m+2} [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$,
 $N_s euNeScFu(\nu^*) = \frac{1}{3s} \left[\sum_{i=1}^s [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$, where s is the number of element of ν^* and
 $N_s euNeScFu(\nu^{**}) = \frac{1}{3t} \left[\sum_{i=1}^t [1 - \mu_i + \sigma_i + \gamma_i] \right]$, where t is the number of element of ν^{**} . For
 $k = 1, 2, \dots, p$,

$N_s euNeScFu(\nu_k)$

$$= \begin{cases} N_s euNeScFu(\nu) & \text{if } N_s euNeScFu(\nu^*) = 0; N_s euNeScFu(\nu^{**}) = 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} [N_s euNeScFu(\nu) + N_s euNeScFu(\nu^*)] & \text{if } N_s euNeScFu(\nu^{**}) = 0 \\ \frac{1}{3} [N_s euNeScFu(\nu) + N_s euNeScFu(\nu^*) + N_s euNeScFu(\nu^{**})] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Step 4: Final Decision

Arrange neutrosophic negative score values for the alternatives $\tau_1 \geq \tau_2 \geq \dots \geq \tau_n$ and the attributes $\nu_1 \geq \nu_2 \geq \dots \geq \nu_p$. Choose the attribute ν_p for the alternative τ_1 and ν_{p-1} for the alternative τ_2 etc. If $n < p$, then ignore ν_k , where $k = 1, 2, \dots, n - p$.

4. Numerical Example

Medical diagnosis has expanded the number of data available to medical professionals as a result of new medical advancements, which also includes vulnerabilities. The path towards grouping multiple sets of symptoms under a single term of a disease is a particularly tough issue in medical diagnosis. In this section, we demonstrate the usefulness and application of the neutrosophic negative score function technique to a medical diagnosis problem.

Step 1: Problem field selection:

Consider the following tables giving informations when consulted physicians about five patients, Patient 1 (shortly, Pat₁), Patient 2 (shortly, Pat₂), Patient 3 (shortly, Pat₃), Patient 4 (shortly, Pat₄) and Patient 5 (shortly, Pat₅) and symptoms are Weight gain (shortly, Wg), Tiredness (shortly, Td), Myalgia (shortly, Ml), Swelling of legs (shortly, Sl) and Mensus Problem (shortly, Mp). We need to find the patient and to find the disease such as Lymphedema, Insomnia, Hypothyroidism, Menarche, Arthritis of the patient. The data in Table 1 and Table 2 are explained by the membership, the indeterminacy and the non-membership functions of the patients and diseases respectively.

Symptoms \ Patients	Pat ₁	Pat ₂	Pat ₃	Pat ₄	Pat ₅
Wg	(0.9,0.1,0)	(0.8,0,0.2)	(0,0.1,0.9)	(0.1,0,0.7)	(0.3,0.2,0.5)
Td	(0,0.3,0.7)	(0.1,0.2,0.7)	(0.8,0.1,0.2)	(0.1,0.1,0.8)	(0.6,0.5,0.3)
Ml	(0.3,0.1,0.6)	(0.8,0,0.3)	(0.3,0.1,0.6)	(0.2,0.1,0.6)	(0.3,0.4,0.4)
Sl	(0.9,0,0.1)	(0.4,0.2,0.5)	(0.2,0.2,0.7)	(0.4,0.2,0.5)	(0.4,0.6,0.3)
Mp	(0.2,0.1,0.7)	(0.3,0.2,0.5)	(0.4,0.3,0.2)	(0.9,0,0.1)	(0.7,0.4,0.5)

TABLE 1. Neutrosophic values for patients

Disease \ Symptoms	Wg	Td	Ml	Sl	Mp
Lymphedema	(0,0.2,0.8)	(0.2,0.2,0.1)	(0.7,0.2,0.1)	(0.9,0,0.1)	(0.2,0.6,0.4)
Insomnia	(0,0.1,0.9)	(0.9,0,0.1)	(0.2,0,0.8)	(0.2,0.4,0.1)	(0.2,0.1,0.7)
Hypothyroidism	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.1,0.1,0.8)	(0,0.1,0.9)	(0.1,0.4,0.3)	(0.2,0.6,0.4)
Menarche	(0.6,0.3,0.1)	(0.1,0.1,0.8)	(0.2,0.4,0.1)	(0.2,0.5,0.3)	(0.9,0,0.2)
Arthritis	(0,0.1,0.8)	(0.1,0.4,0.6)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.1,0.3,0.5)	(0.3,0.1,0.6)

TABLE 2. Neutrosophic values for diseases

Step 2: From neutrosophic topologies for (τ_j) and (ν_k):

(i) τ₁^{*} = τ ∪ τ^{*} ∪ τ^{**}, where

$$\tau = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.9, 0.1, 0), (0, 0.3, 0.7), (0.3, 0.1, 0.6), (0.9, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0.1, 0.7)\},$$

$$\tau^* = \{(0.9, 0.3, 0), (0.3, 0.3, 0.6), (0.9, 0.3, 0.1), (0.2, 0.3, 0.7), (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\tau^{**} = \{(0, 0.1, 0.7), (0, 0, 0.7), (0.3, 0, 0.6), (0.2, 0, 0.7)\}.$$

(ii) τ₂^{*} = τ ∪ τ^{*} ∪ τ^{**}, where

$$\tau = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.8, 0, 0.2), (0.1, 0.2, 0.7), (0.8, 0, 0.2), (0.4, 0.2, 0.5), (0.3, 0.2, 0.5)\},$$

$$\tau^* = \{(0.8, 0.2, 0.2), (0.8, 0.2, 0.3)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\tau^{**} = \{(0.1, 0, 0.7), (0.4, 0, 0.5), (0.3, 0, 0.5)\}.$$

(iii) τ₃^{*} = τ ∪ τ^{*} ∪ τ^{**}, where

$$\tau = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0, 0.1, 0.9), (0.8, 0.1, 0.2), (0.3, 0.1, 0.6), (0.2, 0.2, 0.7), (0.4, 0.3, 0.2)\},$$

FIGURE 1. Neutrosophic values for Patient 1

FIGURE 2. Neutrosophic values for Patient 2

FIGURE 3. Neutrosophic values for Patient 3

$$\tau^* = \{(0.8, 0.2, 0.2), (0.8, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.2, 0.6)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\tau^{**} = h\{(0.2, 0.1, 0.7), (0.4, 0.1, 0.2)\}.$$

(iv) $\tau_4^* = \tau \cup \tau^* \cup \tau^{**}$, where

$$\tau = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.1, 0, 0.7), (0.1, 0.1, 0.8), (0.2, 0.1, 0.6), (0.4, 0.2, 0.5), (0.9, 0, 0.1)\},$$

$$\tau^* = \{(0.1, 0.1, 0.7), (0.9, 0.1, 0.1), (0.9, 0.2, 0.1)\} \text{ and}$$

FIGURE 4. Neutrosophic values for Patient 4

FIGURE 5. Neutrosophic values for Patient 5

FIGURE 6. Neutrosophic values for Lymphedema

$$\tau^{**} = \{(0.1, 0, 0.8), (0.2, 0, 0.6), (0.4, 0, 0.5)\}.$$

$$(v) \tau_5^* = \tau \cup \tau^* \cup \tau^{**}, \text{ where } \tau = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.3, 0.2, 0.5), (0.6, 0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.6, 0.3), (0.7, 0.4, 0.5)\},$$

$$\tau^* = \{(0.6, 0.6, 0.3), (0.7, 0.5, 0.3), (0.7, 0.4, 0.4), (0.7, 0.6, 0.3)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\tau^{**} = \{(0.4, 0.5, 0.3), (0.6, 0.4, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.5), (0.4, 0.4, 0.5)\}.$$

$$(i) \nu_1^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}, \text{ where}$$

$$\nu = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0, 0.2, 0.8), (0.2, 0.2, 0.1), (0.7, 0.2, 0.1), (0.9, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0.6, 0.4)\},$$

FIGURE 7. Neutrosophic values for Insomnia

FIGURE 8. Neutrosophic values for Hypothyroidism

FIGURE 9. Neutrosophic values for Menarche

$\nu^* = \{(0.9, 0.2, 0.1), (0.2, 0.6, 0.1), (0.7, 0.6, 0.1), (0.9, 0.6, 0.1)\}$ and

$\nu^{**} = \{(0, 0, 0.8), (0.2, 0.2, 0.1), (0.2, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0.2, 0.4), (0.7, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0, 0.4)\}$.

(ii) $\nu_2^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}$, where

$\nu = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0, 0.1, 0.9), (0.9, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.1), (0.2, 0.1, 0.7)\}$,

$\nu^* = \{(0.9, 0.1, 0.1), (0.2, 0.1, 0.8), (0.9, 0.4, 0.1)\}$ and

$\nu^{**} = \{(0, 0, 0.9), (0.2, 0, 0.1), (0.2, 0, 0.7)\}$.

(iii) $\nu_3^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}$, where

FIGURE 10. Neutrosophic values for Arthritis

$$\nu = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.9, 0.1, 0.1), (0.1, 0.1, 0.8), (0, 0.1, 0.9), (0.1, 0.4, 0.3), (0.2, 0.6, 0.4)\},$$

$$\nu^* = \{(0.9, 0.4, 0.1), (0.9, 0.6, 0.1), (0.2, 0.6, 0.3)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\nu^{**} = \{(0.1, 0.1, 0.3), (0.2, 0.1, 0.4), (0, 0.1, 0.9), (0.1, 0.4, 0.4)\}.$$

(iv) $\nu_4^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}$, where

$$\nu = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0.6, 0.3, 0.1), (0.1, 0.1, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.1), (0.2, 0.5, 0.3), (0.9, 0, 0.2)\},$$

$$\nu^* = \{(0.6, 0.4, 0.1), (0.6, 0.5, 0.1), (0.9, 0.3, 0.1), (0.9, 0.1, 0.2), (0.2, 0.5, 0.1), (0.9, 0.4, 0.1), (0.9, 0.5, 0.2)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\nu^{**} = \{(0.2, 0.3, 0.1), (0.2, 0.3, 0.3), (0.6, 0, 0.2), (0.1, 0, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.3), (0.2, 0.4, 0.2)\}.$$

(v) $\nu_5^* = \nu \cup \nu^* \cup \nu^{**}$, where

$$\nu = \{(0, 0, 1), (1, 1, 0), (0, 0.1, 0.8), (0.1, 0.4, 0.6), (0.9, 0.1, 0.1), (0.1, 0.3, 0.5), (0.3, 0.1, 0.6)\},$$

$$\nu^* = \{(0.9, 0.4, 0.1), (0.1, 0.4, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.6), (0.9, 0.3, 0.1), (0.3, 0.3, 0.5)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\nu^{**} = \{(0.1, 0.1, 0.6), (0.1, 0.3, 0.6), (0.1, 0.1, 0.5)\}.$$

Step 3: Find neutrosophic negative score functions:

(i) $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau) = 0.4$, $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^*) = 0.3067$ and $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^{**}) = 0.525$.

$$N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau_1) = 0.4106.$$

(ii) $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau) = 0.4$, $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^*) = 0.2167$ and $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^{**}) = 0.4334$.

$$N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau_2) = 0.3501.$$

(iii) $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau) = 0.4619$, $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^*) = 0.3112$ and $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^{**}) = 0.4167$.

$$N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau_3) = 0.3966.$$

(iv) $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau) = 0.4476$, $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^*) = 0.2667$ and $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^{**}) = 0.4667$.

$$N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau_4) = 0.3937.$$

(v) $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau) = 0.4467$, $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^*) = 0.3917$ and $N_{seuNeScFu}(\tau^{**}) = 0.4834$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\tau_5) = 0.4473.$$

(i) $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu) = 0.4143$, $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^*) = 0.3083$ and $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^{**}) = 0.4143$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu_1) = 0.3668.$$

(ii) $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu) = 0.4619$, $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^*) = 0.2889$ and $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^{**}) = 0.4778$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu_2) = 0.4095.$$

(iii) $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu) = 0.5$, $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^*) = 0.3445$ and $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^{**}) = 0.525$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu_3) = 0.4565.$$

(iv) $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu) = 0.4191$, $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^*) = 0.2334$ and $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^{**}) = 0.4112$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu_4) = 0.3546.$$

(v) $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu) = 0.4857$, $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^*) = 0.4067$ and $N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu^{**}) = 0.5445$.

$$N_s eu Ne Sc Fu(\nu_5) = 0.479.$$

FIGURE 11. Neutrosophic negative score values for Patients

FIGURE 12. Neutrosophic negative score values for Diseases

Step 4: Final Decision:

Arrange neutrosophic negative score values for the alternatives $\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \tau_4, \tau_5$ and the attributes $\nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3, \nu_4, \nu_5$ in descending order. We get the following sequences $\tau_5 \leq \tau_1 \leq \tau_3 \leq \tau_4 \leq \tau_2$ and $\nu_5 \leq \nu_3 \leq \nu_2 \leq \nu_1 \leq \nu_4$. Thus the Pat₅ suffers from Menarche, the Pat₁ suffers from Lymphedema, the Pat₃ suffers from Insomnia, the Pat₄ suffers from Hypothyroidism and the Pat₂ suffers from Arthritis.

5. Conclusions

One of the research areas in general fuzzy topological spaces dealing with the concept of vagueness is neutrosophic topological space. This study established the neutrosophic negative scoring function and the technique based on qualities, as well as alternatives to its real-world application. In addition, the medical diagnosis decision-making problem employing qualities and choices on the neutrosophic score function. This theory can be developed and applied to other general topology study areas such as rough topology, digital topology, image processing, neural networks, and so on. Furthermore, the neutrosophic accuracy function and neutrosophic certainty function are based on applications that can be carried out in future studies.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to thank the editors and the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments and suggestions which have helped immensely in improving the quality of the paper.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. M. Abdel-Basset, V. Chang, M. Mohamed and F. Smarandache, *A Refined Approach for Forecasting Based on Neutrosophic Time Series*, Symmetry, **11** (4) (2019), 457.
2. M. Abdel-Basset, G. Manogaran, A. Gamal and V. Chang, *A Novel Intelligent Medical Decision Support Model Based on Soft Computing and IoT*, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, (2019).
3. M. Abdel-Basset, and M. Mohamed, *A novel and powerful framework based on neutrosophic sets to aid patients with cancer*, Future Generation Computer Systems, **98** (2019) 144-153.
4. M. Abdel-Basset, A. Gamal, G. Manogaran and H. V. Long *A novel group decision making model based on neutrosophic sets for heart disease diagnosis*, Multimedia Tools and Applications, (2019) 1-26.
5. M. Abdel-Basset, G. Manogaran, A. Gamal and F. Smarandache, *A group decision making framework based on neutrosophic TOPSIS approach for smart medical device selection*, Journal of medical systems, **43** (2)(2019), 1-13.
6. K. P. Adlassnig, *Fuzzy set theory in medical diagnosis*, IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, **16** (2) (1986), 260-265.
7. K. Atanassov, *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets*, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, **20** (1986), 87-96.
8. P. Biswas, S. Pramanik and B. C. Giri, *A study on information technology professionals' health problem based on intuitionistic fuzzy cosine similarity measure*, Swiss Journal of Statistical and Applied Mathematics, **2** (1) (2014), 44-50.

9. S. Broumi and F. Smarandache, *Several similarity measures of neutrosophic sets*, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **1** (2013), 54-62.
10. C. L. Chang, *Fuzzy topological spaces*, J. Math. Anal. Appl., **24** (1968), 182-190.
11. V. Chinnadurai and A. Bobin, *Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis Process by Using Prospect Decision Theory in Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Environment*, CAAI Trans. Intell. Technol., **5** (3) (2020), 209-221.
12. V. Chinnadurai and A. Bobin, *Single-valued neutrosophic N -soft set and intertemporal single-valued neutrosophic N -soft set to assess and pre-assess the mental health of students amidst COVID-19*, Neutrosophic sets and systems, **38** (2020), 67-110.
13. V. Chinnadurai, F. Smarandache and A. Bobin, *Multi-Aspect Decision-Making Process in Equity Investment Using Neutrosophic Soft Matrices*, Neutrosophic sets and systems, **31** (2020), 224-241.
14. D. Coker, *An introduction to intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces*, Fuzzy sets and systems, **88** (1997), 81-89.
15. S. K. De, A. Biswas and R. Roy, *An application of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in medical diagnosis*, Fuzzy Sets and System, **117** (2) (2001), 209-213.
16. P. R. Innocent and R. I. John, *Computer aided fuzzy medical diagnosis*, Information Sciences, **162** (2004), 81-104.
17. V. Khatibi and G. A. Montazer, *Intuitionistic fuzzy set vs fuzzy set application in medical pattern recognition*, Artificial Intelligence in Medicine, **47** (1) (2009), 43-52.
18. P. Majumdar and S. K. Samanta, *On similarity and entropy of neutrosophic sets*, Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems, **26** (3) (2014), 1245-1252.
19. N. A. Nabeeh, F. Smarandache, M. Abdel-Basset, H. A. El-Ghareeb and A. Aboelfetouh, *An Integrated Neutrosophic-TOPSIS Approach and Its Application to Personnel Selection: A New Trend in Brain Processing and Analysis*, IEEE Access, **7** (2019), 29734-29744.
20. T.J. Roos, *Fuzzy Logic with Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill P.C., New York, 1994.
21. A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi, *Neutrosophic set and neutrosophic topological spaces*, IOSR Journal of Mathematics, **3** (4) (2012), 31-35.
22. A. A. Salama and F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophic crisp set theory*, Educational Publisher, Columbus, Ohio, USA, 2015.
23. F. Smarandache, *A Unifying field in logics: neutrosophic logic. neutrosophy, neutrosophic set, neutrosophic probability*, American Research Press, Rehoboth, NM, (1999).
24. F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophy and neutrosophic logic*, First International Conference on Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Logic, Set, Probability, and Statistics, University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM 87301, USA (2002).
25. F. Smarandache, *The Score, Accuracy, and Certainty Functions determine a Total Order on the Set of Neutrosophic Triplets (T, I, F)* , Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **38** (2020), 1-14.
26. M. Sugeno, *An Introductory survey of fuzzy control*, Information sciences, **36** (1985), 59-83.
27. E. Szmidi and J. Kacprzyk, *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets in some medical applications*, In International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg (2001), 148-151.
28. N. D. Thanh and M. Ali, *Neutrosophic recommender system for medical diagnosis based on algebraic similarity measure and clustering*, In Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE), IEEE International Conference, (2017), 1-6.
29. A. Vadivel and C. John Sundar, *Neutrosophic δ -Open Maps and Neutrosophic δ -Closed Maps*, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science (IJNS), **13** (2) (2021), 66-74.
30. A. Vadivel and C. John Sundar, *New Operators Using Neutrosophic δ -Open Set*, Journal of Neutrosophic and Fuzzy Systems, **1** (2) (2021), 61-70.
31. A. Vadivel and C. John Sundar, *Application of Neutrosophic Sets Based on Mobile Network Using Neutrosophic Functions*, Emerging Trends in Industry 4.0 (ETI 4.0), (2021), 1-8.

32. A. Vadivel, N. Moogambigai, S. Tamilselvan and P. Thangaraja, *Application of Neutrosophic Sets Based on Neutrosophic Score Function in Material Selection*, 2022 First International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Information and Communication Technologies (ICEEICT), (2022), 1-5.
33. A. Vadivel, M. Seenivasan and C. John Sundar, *An introduction to δ -open sets in a neutrosophic topological spaces*, Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **1724** (2021), 012011.
34. A. Vadivel, P. Thangaraja and C. John Sundar, *Neutrosophic e -continuous maps and neutrosophic e -irresolute maps*, Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education, **12** (1S) (2021), 369-375.
35. A. Vadivel, P. Thangaraja and C. John Sundar, *Neutrosophic e -Open Maps, Neutrosophic e -Closed Maps and Neutrosophic e -Homeomorphisms in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces*, AIP Conference Proceedings, **2364** (2021), 020016.
36. V. Venkateswaran Rao and Y. Srinivasa Rao, *Neutrosophic Pre-open sets and Pre-closed sets in Neutrosophic Topology*, International Journal of chemTech Research, **10** (10), 449-458.
37. F. Wadei, Al-Omeri and Saeid Jafari, *Neutrosophic pre-continuity multifunctions and almost pre-continuity multifunctions*, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **27** (2019), 53-69.
38. H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y. Zhang and R. Sunderraman, *Single valued neutrosophic sets*, Multi-space and Multi-structure, **4** (2010), 410-413.
39. J. Ye and Q. Zhang, *Single valued neutrosophic similarity measures for multiple attribute decision-making*, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **2** (2014), 48-54.
40. J. Ye and S. Ye, *Medical diagnosis using distance-based similarity measures of single valued neutrosophic multisets*, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, **7** (2015), 47-54.
41. L. A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy sets*, Information and control, **8** (1965), 338-353.

Received: April 2, 2023. Accepted: July 19, 2023